

1 **Sestrin modulation denotes alternative nutrient sensing strategies during lineage commitment in**
2 **the human embryo.**

3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of the
9 Sestrins as lineage commitment cooperating factors in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo. This
10 included SESN1 and SESN3.

11 Citations

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